

GYMNASTICS FOR CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE

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Abstract. Physical activity has the best effect on a child's health, and it is a proven fact that they tire the body, train willpower and strengthen character. But how to determine the limit of feasibility, how to determine what kind of sport is useful for a child and, conversely, what is inappropriate for a child. Recently, gymnastics for children has become popular, especially among parents and teachers, who began to engage in it almost from the cradle. Gymnastics classes are held in kindergartens, schools and child development centers, but is it as cool as the teachers say? What is good and bad in this sport, and at what age can and should do it? The answers are in the article.

Key words: gymnastics, artistic gymnastics, sports, flexibility, finesse.

ГИМНАСТИКА ДЛЯ ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

Аннотация. Физические нагрузки наилучшим образом сказываются на здоровье ребенка, и это доказанный факт, что они утомляют организм, тренируют силу воли и укрепляют характер. Но как определить предел осуществимости, как определить, какой вид спорта полезен для ребенка и, наоборот, какой ему не подходит? В последнее время гимнастика для детей стала популярной, особенно среди родителей и педагогов, которые начали заниматься ею чуть ли не с пеленок. Занятия гимнастикой проводятся в детских садах, школах и центрах развития детей, но так ли это круто, как говорят учителя? Что хорошо и что плохо в этом виде спорта, и в каком возрасте можно и нужно этим заниматься? Ответы приведены в статье.

Ключевые слова: гимнастика, художественная гимнастика, спорт, гибкость, фитнес.

If it is not possible to study the child's abilities, then it is necessary to rely on the opinion of coaches and leaders of sports schools for children and teenagers. Experienced professionals see their future trainees from the beginning, even during acquaintances they can predict the future success of the athlete.

Before recruiting to groups, coaches evaluate candidates, they do not take everyone to their department. They organize such weddings for children. Gymnastics is a special type of sport. It is divided into artistic and sports. The first, as a rule, is done by girls because of its aesthetics. Girls also go to gymnastics, but there are still many boys.

To practice this sport, you need to apply in several ways:

- having a thin body;
- strong hands;
- narrow pelvis;
- have sufficient flexibility and plasticity;
- performing basic gymnastic exercises - somersaults, hanging on a stick or pulling.

It is believed that gymnastics for children is the best start in the future, even if the child does not stay in gymnastics. From what age can a child be sent to the sports department? The first physical education classes are given to children in kindergarten. Gymnastics for children aged 3-4 is included in the compulsory program of preschool educational institutions. However, you should understand that training there is selected taking into account the age characteristics of children. In different development groups, children are involved from the youngest kindergarten age. Such events are far from professional sports, which have strict age restrictions set by Soviet standards. According to them, children of at least five years of age are admitted to CYSS. Gymnastics is a sport where you can get as many shredders as you want. In team sections, such as football, basketball or volleyball, children are accepted at school age - after 8-9 years old, and serious sports are allowed only from 10-12 years old. These rules are made for a reason, they have several explanations at once:

- children are able to adequately perceive and listen to the coach's instructions and recommendations only after the age of 6;
- babies are overexcited in training and competitions, and their musculoskeletal system is not yet fully formed, so strong physical effort does not benefit their body, but harms it.

According to traumatologists and orthopedists, the most suitable sports for children of primary school age are athletics, swimming, fitness and dance. This list does not include gymnastics for a reason. Exercise is full of sprains and other injuries that start to haunt a child at a young age. Gymnastics is an ideal sport for a child's all-round development.

At the same time, if you approach training wisely, do not believe in the sports of achievements, then gymnastics can bring undeniable benefits to the growing body. With its help, children learn to coordinate movements, develop not only physically, but also mentally.

Reserve exercises have a beneficial effect on the tone of the body. A child who does not sit in one place, but regularly performs various gymnastic exercises, improves appetite, mood and normalizes sleep.

We are not talking about power loads, but about high-quality physical activity. Gymnastics for 4-year-old children (plus or minus a year) should include the following exercises:

- Walk;
- Light jogging;
- Drowning;
- Jumping;
- Twists and turns of the body;
- Shake your hands (to the sides, forward and up);
- Kicks and punches.

Sports equipment helps to diversify classes - balls, dumbbells, rings, jump ropes, sticks, fitballs. Rhythmic gymnastics: what it is and who can do it, as opposed to rhythmic.

Gymnastics sticks with small clubs, ribbons, balls and hoops are used as the main "working" equipment of artistic gymnasts. During the show, the girls not only perform various exercises to demonstrate their stretch and exercise physical strength, but also it is necessary to show how dexterous and artistic they are in managing props while coordinating their many actions.

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